

Environmental Persistence of Typhoid and Barriers to Treatment-Seeking: An Eco-Health Study in Pankshin Local Government Area of Plateau state, Nigeria

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Abstract

Typhoid fever remains a persistent public health challenge in low-income and middle-income countries, driven by unsafe water, poor sanitation, weak health systems, and socio-cultural factors. In Nigeria, limited surveillance, inadequate diagnostic capacity, and growing antimicrobial resistance further complicate disease control, particularly in rural settings. This study examined the environmental, socio-cultural, and healthcare-related factors influencing the persistence of typhoid fever and treatment-seeking behaviour in rural communities of Pankshin Local Government Area (LGA), Plateau State, Nigeria. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in eight rural and peri-urban communities of Pankshin LGA. Eighty adult residents (≥ 18 years), selected purposively, were interviewed using a structured questionnaire assessing knowledge and perceptions of typhoid, perceived frequency and severity, treatment-seeking behaviour, and barriers to care. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential tests in R software, while Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques were used to map study locations and spatial patterns. The results showed that most respondents (60.5%) correctly identified contaminated food and water as the main causes of typhoid, although misconceptions such as witchcraft (26.7%) and mosquito transmission (11.6%) persisted. Typhoid was perceived as frequent by 68.6% of respondents, and 75.6% reported knowing someone who had undergone surgery due to typhoid-related complications. While hospitals were the preferred first point of care for most respondents (73.3%), a substantial proportion relied on herbal medicine or chemist shops (40.7%). Cost (55.8%), belief in alternative treatment, and distance to health facilities were the main barriers to hospital utilization. Although confidence in local health centres was relatively high, structural and economic constraints continued to drive delayed or inappropriate care. The study concluded that typhoid fever remains endemic in rural Pankshin LGA, sustained by environmental exposure, economic hardship, health system limitations, and persistent socio-cultural beliefs. Addressing typhoid burden requires

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integrated eco-health-informed interventions that combine improved water and sanitation, strengthened primary healthcare services, affordable diagnostics and treatment, and targeted community health education to reduce misconceptions and improve timely care-seeking.

Keywords: *Typhoid, Barriers, Treatment-seeking, Eco-health, Environmental persistence.*

Introduction

Typhoid fever is a severe systemic infectious disease caused by *Salmonella typhi*, a Gram-negative, oxidase-negative bacterium. Transmission occurs predominantly via the faeco-oral route through the ingestion of contaminated food and water. Globally, typhoid fever was estimated to account for approximately 26.9 million cases and 217,000 deaths in 2010, even after adjusting for blood culture sensitivity (Buckle et al., 2012; Breiman et al., 2012, (Mogasale et al., 2014). An estimated 33 million cases of typhoid fever occur each year globally, leading to approximately 216,000 deaths, particularly in endemic regions. Typhoid outbreaks are commonly reported in sub-Saharan Africa and parts of Southeast Asia. It remains a significant global public health concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where environmental conditions, inadequate sanitation, and weak health systems facilitate sustained transmission (Ia & Mo, 2020).

The World Health Organization recognizes typhoid fever as a major public health concern, with a high disease burden among children, young adults, and pregnant women. Clinically, the disease is characterized by a progressively rising fever, which is its most distinctive feature. Other frequently observed symptoms include high-grade fever, lethargy, skin rash, reduced appetite, constipation (more commonly than diarrhea), abdominal pain, diarrhea, hepatosplenomegaly, bradycardia, and headache. In the absence of appropriate treatment, these symptoms may persist for several weeks or even months (World Health Organization (WHO), 2014; Ubengama et al., 2019; Ia & Mo, 2020). Despite these figures, global understanding of typhoid epidemiology remains incomplete, particularly in regions where surveillance systems are weak (Antillón et al., 2017).

Geographically, south-central and east-central Asia have been identified as regions with the highest incidence of typhoid fever, exceeding 100 cases per 100,000 population annually, while Africa has been classified as having a moderate but poorly characterized burden, estimated at 10–100 cases per 100,000 people (Marks et al., 2017). However, the African continent remains underrepresented in global typhoid burden estimates, with only limited data historically available from countries such as Egypt and South Africa (Buckle et al., 2012; Breiman et al., 2012). This lack of robust epidemiological data prompted the World Health Organization to call for a continent-wide effort to generate reliable incidence and antimicrobial resistance data for invasive *Salmonella* infections in Africa (World Health Organization, 2008).

In sub-Saharan Africa, rapid urbanization, environmental degradation, unsafe water sources, inadequate sanitation, and poor waste management continue to create conditions conducive to the persistence and transmission of typhoid fever. Environmental risks such as flooding, water pollution, air pollution, and waste accumulation have been shown to directly influence sanitation-related and waterborne diseases, particularly in vulnerable communities (Wafula, 2022). These environmental determinants are further intensified by climate variability, with evidence linking seasonal rainfall patterns, rising temperatures, and flooding to increased typhoid transmission (Ekpenyong & Akpan, 2023; Omoregie & Okoro, 2024). Such findings highlight the relevance of integrative frameworks such as the Eco-Health approach, which emphasizes the interconnectedness of environmental conditions, human behaviour, and health outcomes.

Nigeria bears a disproportionate share of the typhoid burden in West Africa due to a combination of environmental, socioeconomic, and health system challenges. Factors such as inadequate access to potable water, poor sanitation infrastructure, rapid population growth, unregulated urban expansion, and overburdened healthcare services have sustained typhoid transmission across both rural and urban settings (Talabi, 1994; Akinyemi et al., 2005). Although reported prevalence rates vary widely across states from as low as 0.071% in Oyo State to as high as 47.1% in Osun State these figures likely underestimate the true burden due to weak surveillance systems and limited diagnostic capacity (Talabi, 1994; Akinyemi et al., 2005; Kabir'O et al., 2000; Kingsley et al., 2013; Obaro et al., 2015).

Accurate estimation of typhoid burden relies heavily on blood culture confirmation, yet such diagnostic services are largely restricted to referral hospitals in Nigeria. As a result, many cases are treated empirically, often leading to prolonged illness, hospitalization, and increased risk of complications due to treatment failure (Adeleye & Adetosoye, 1993). The emergence and spread of multidrug-resistant *S. Typhi* strains, including resistance to first-line antibiotics and fluoroquinolones, have further complicated typhoid management in Nigeria and across Africa (Adeleye & Adetosoye, 1993; Oboegbulam et al., 1995; Feasey et al., 2012). Evidence from Lagos, Abuja, and Kano indicates persistently high levels of antimicrobial resistance, with over 80% of isolates in some settings exhibiting multidrug resistance (Akinyemi et al., 2018).

Environmental persistence of *S. Typhi* is strongly linked to unsafe food handling practices, contaminated water sources, and poor sanitation (Buzilă et al., 2025). Food handlers have been identified as critical agents in typhoid transmission, underscoring the importance of hygiene education and environmental health regulation (Smith et al., 2010; Buzilă et al., 2025). Inadequate access to essential amenities, particularly clean water, remains a major driver of infection in many Nigerian communities (Ilouno, 2020). Seasonal patterns further exacerbate disease risk, with increased incidence observed during warmer months and peak rainfall periods, when flooding and water contamination are most pronounced (Ekpenyong & Akpan, 2023; Okeke & Eze, 2021; Nwidi et al., 2020; Ogbonna et al., 2023). Beyond environmental exposure, treatment-seeking behaviour plays a crucial role in shaping typhoid outcomes. Evidence suggests that individuals in low-income communities often adopt pluralistic health-seeking strategies, combining modern medical care with traditional remedies (Asenowo & Adeoye, 2025). Economic constraints, perceived severity of illness, environmental conditions, occupation, and place of residence significantly influence decisions regarding care-seeking and treatment pathways (Asenowo & Adeoye, 2025). These dynamics are particularly evident in rural settings, where limited healthcare access and strong socio-cultural beliefs may delay appropriate clinical management.

Given the persistent burden of typhoid fever in Nigeria, the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance, and the strong influence of environmental and behavioural factors, there is an urgent need for integrated, eco-health-informed approaches to disease control. This study therefore examines the environmental persistence of typhoid fever and the barriers to treatment-seeking behaviour in eight rural Nigerian communities, with a focus on understanding how ecological conditions, socio-economic factors, and health system constraints interact to shape disease risk and management.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the environmental, socio-cultural, and healthcare-related factors influencing the persistence of typhoid fever and treatment-seeking behaviour in rural communities of Pankshin Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. assess community knowledge and perceptions regarding the causes and transmission of typhoid fever in rural communities of Pankshin LGA;
2. examine the perceived frequency and severity of typhoid fever and the occurrence of typhoid-related complications within the study communities;
3. analyse treatment-seeking behaviour and the pattern of healthcare utilisation for typhoid fever among rural residents;
4. identify the key environmental, socio-economic, and structural barriers influencing access to timely and appropriate treatment for typhoid fever.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of knowledge and what perceptions do community members hold regarding the causes and transmission of typhoid fever?
2. How frequently does typhoid fever occur in the study communities, and what is the perceived severity and burden of typhoid-related complications?
3. What treatment-seeking behaviours and healthcare options are commonly adopted by rural residents in managing typhoid fever?
4. What environmental, socio-economic, and health system barriers influence access to effective and timely treatment for typhoid fever in the study area?

Study Area

This study was carried out in selected rural and peri-urban communities of Pankshin Local Government Area (LGA), Plateau State, located in north-central Nigeria. Pankshin LGA lies on the Jos Plateau between approximately latitude 9°18'–9°35' N and longitude 9°15'–9°40' E, covering an estimated land area of about 1,524 km² (Nwankwo et al. 2024). According to the 2006 national census, the LGA had a population of about 191,685, with steady population growth recorded over the years due to natural increase and rural–urban interactions (Nwankwo et al. 2024).

Pankshin LGA is predominantly rural, characterised by undulating highlands, rocky outcrops, valleys, and extensive farmlands. Its location on the Jos Plateau confers a relatively moderate climate compared to surrounding lowland areas, with distinct wet and dry seasons that strongly influence agricultural activities and water availability.

The local economy is largely agrarian, with residents engaged in subsistence and small-scale commercial farming of crops such as maize, millet, rice, tomatoes, and onions, alongside livestock rearing and petty trading. Settlements are mostly dispersed, and access to potable water, sanitation facilities, and healthcare services varies considerably across communities, particularly in more remote areas.

Pankshin LGA is ethnically and culturally diverse, inhabited by the indigenous groups like the Ngas, Mupun, Miship, Fier, Tal, Kadung, Rom (Tambes) and Pai. Other migrant ethnic groups like the Igbos, Yorubas, Bogghoms, Beroms, Goemai, Idomas, Taroh, etc can also be found in the LGA. Religiously, Christianity as the dominant religion, alongside African Traditional Religion, ATR (indigenous belief systems) and Islam, continue to shape social norms and health-seeking behaviour. Geographically, the Pankshin LGA shares boundaries with Mangu, Tafawa Balewa, Kanke, Langtang North, Mikang, Shendam, and Qua'an Pan Local Government Areas, positioning it as an important link between agricultural communities in southern and eastern Plateau State. The environmental conditions, livelihood patterns, and socio-cultural diversity of Pankshin LGA make it a suitable setting for examining

community perceptions, environmental risk factors, and treatment-seeking behaviour related to typhoid fever.

Figure 1. Map of Pankshin LGA, Plateau state, Nigeria showing the study Locations

Methodology

Study Design and Setting

This research adopted a community-based cross-sectional study design to assess awareness, knowledge, and treatment-seeking behaviour related to typhoid among rural populations in Pankshin Local Government Area (LGA), Plateau State, north-central Nigeria. The study was conducted in eight rural communities, deliberately selected to capture variations in geographical location, cultural background, and access to health services within the LGA. Although the study sites and communities are the same as those used in previous work, this investigation addresses a different research focus.

Study Population and Sampling Technique

The study population comprised adult residents aged 18 years and above who had lived in their respective communities for at least ten years. A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants in each community. Ten (10) respondents were recruited per community, resulting in a total sample size of 80 participants. This approach ensured the inclusion of respondents with varied socio-demographic characteristics, including differences in age, sex, educational attainment, and occupation. Only individuals who voluntarily consented to participate were enrolled in the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed specifically for this study. The instrument covered sections on socio-demographic characteristics, level of awareness and knowledge of typhoid, perceived causes and severity of the disease, treatment-seeking behaviour, and challenges associated with accessing clinical care. To ensure content and face validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in public health, epidemiology, and social sciences. Their inputs helped refine the wording, relevance, and cultural suitability of the questions for rural community settings.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the questionnaire was evaluated using the test–retest reliability method. The instrument was first administered to 10 respondents in a pilot rural community not included in the main study and re-administered after an interval of two weeks. Responses from both administrations were analysed using Pearson’s correlation coefficient, which produced a strong correlation value ($r \geq 0.85$), indicating good consistency and stability of the instrument over time.

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection was carried out through face-to-face interviews conducted by trained field assistants familiar with the local language and culture. This approach minimized misunderstanding and improved response accuracy, particularly among respondents with limited literacy. In addition, the geographical coordinates of respondents’ households were recorded using Garmin eTrex 10 GPS receivers. These spatial data were used to support geographic analysis and mapping of the study locations.

Data Management and Analysis

Completed questionnaires were checked for completeness and entered into Microsoft Excel before being exported for statistical analysis using the latest version of R statistical software (R version 4.5.2). Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarise respondents’ characteristics and key study variables. Associations between demographic factors and awareness or treatment-seeking behaviour were examined using chi-square tests or Fisher’s exact tests, where appropriate, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Spatial data obtained from GPS coordinates were imported into ArcGIS Pro (version 3.6) for mapping and visualization. Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques were used to display the spatial distribution of study communities, levels of awareness, and treatment-seeking patterns across the study area, thereby enhancing interpretation of the findings within their geographical context.

Results

Figure 2. Community knowledge and Perceived Causes of Typhoid in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 3. respondents’ knowledge of People who Underwent Surgery as a Result of Typhoid Disease’ Complications in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 4. Responses of Rural People on how often they fell sick with Typhoid disease in Pankshin LGA of Plateau state, Nigeria

Figure 5. Responses of Respondents on How they Treat Typhoid in Communities within Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 6. Reasons for Avoiding Hospital treatment of Typhoid in Rural Communities of Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 7. People's Belief on the Fatality of Typhoid in the Rural communities of Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 8. Respondents' Beliefs on Causes of Chronic Repeated Typhoid Infections in their Rural Communities in Pankshin LGA of Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 9. Initial Health-seeking Behaviour of the People of the Rural Communities in Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 10. Respondents' Confidence in Local Health centers in their communities in Pankshin LGA of Plateau state, Nigeria

Figure 11. Respondents' Belief in Combining Traditional and Orthodox Medicine to Cure Typhoid Disease in Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Figure 12. Responses on the Challenges Leading to choice of Alternative Medicine in the Treatment of Typhoid disease in Rural communities of Pankshin LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria

Community Knowledge and Perceived Causes of Typhoid

As shown in **Fig. 2**, respondents demonstrated mixed perceptions regarding the causes of typhoid fever. The majority, 60.5% (n = 52), identified contaminated water and food as the primary cause, indicating a substantial level of correct biomedical understanding of typhoid transmission. However, notable misconceptions persist, with 26.7% (n = 23) attributing typhoid to witchcraft and 11.6% (n = 10) to mosquito bites, while 1.2% (n = 1) cited overthinking or stress.

Knowledge of Typhoid-Related Surgical Complications

Responses presented in **Fig. 3** indicate that 75.6% (n = 65) of respondents knew someone who had undergone surgery due to typhoid complications, such as intestinal perforation, whereas 24.4% (n = 21) did not. This suggests widespread exposure to severe and advanced manifestations of typhoid fever within the study communities.

Perceived Frequency of Typhoid Occurrence

As illustrated in **Fig. 4**, nearly half of the respondents (45.3%, n = 39) reported that typhoid occurs very often in their communities, while 23.3% (n = 20) indicated it occurs often. In contrast, 25.6% (n = 22) reported occasional occurrence and only 5.8% (n = 5) perceived it as rare. Overall, 68.6% of respondents perceived typhoid as a frequent disease.

Treatment Practices for Typhoid Fever

According to **Fig. 5**, hospital-based treatment was the most commonly reported approach, used by 59.3% (n = 51) of respondents. However, 23.3% (n = 20) relied on herbal medicine, while 17.4% (n = 15) sought treatment from chemist shops. When grouped, 40.7% of respondents depended on informal or alternative treatment pathways.

Reasons for Avoiding Hospital Treatment

As shown in **Fig. 6**, cost was the dominant reason for avoiding hospital treatment, reported by 55.8% of respondents. Other reasons included belief in herbal treatment (18.6%), distance to health facilities (12.8%), lack of trust in doctors (10.5%), and other minor factors (2.3%).

Perceived Fatality of Typhoid Fever

Results in **Fig. 7** show that 88.4% (n = 76) of respondents believed typhoid can cause death, 2.3% (n = 2) believed it cannot, and 9.3% (n = 8) were unsure. This indicates a high level of awareness of the severity of typhoid fever.

Beliefs on Causes of Recurrent Typhoid Infections

As presented in **Fig. 8**, most respondents (79.1%, n = 68) attributed repeated typhoid infections to poor water and sanitation. However, 12.8% associated recurrent infection with witchcraft, 7.0% with “weak blood,” and 1.2% with unprotected sex.

Initial Health-Seeking Behaviour

Data in **Fig. 9** show that hospitals were the first point of care for 73.3% (n = 63) of respondents when sick. Chemist shops were used by 15.1%, herbalists by 7.0%, and prayer houses by 3.5%.

Confidence in Local Health Centres

As indicated in **Fig. 10**, 60.5% (n = 52) of respondents were very confident in their local health centres, while 26.7% were somewhat confident. A minority expressed no confidence (11.6%) or were unsure (1.2%).

Attitudes Toward Integrating Traditional and Orthodox Medicine

Results in **Fig. 11** reveal that 44.2% (n = 38) opposed combining traditional and orthodox medicine, 31.4% supported integration, and 24.4% were unsure.

Challenges Driving the Use of Alternative Medicine

Findings summarized in **Fig. 12** indicate that poor awareness, absence of vaccines, poor health facilities, and high cost of clinical care were major drivers of alternative medicine use, reinforcing the dominance of structural and economic barriers over purely cultural factors.

Discussion

The findings demonstrate that typhoid fever remains a persistent public health problem in rural communities of Pankshin LGA, reflecting broader global and African patterns where typhoid continues to thrive in settings characterized by inadequate water, sanitation, and healthcare access (Antillón et al., 2017; Mogasale et al., 2014). The high proportion of respondents correctly identified contaminated water and food as the main cause of typhoid aligns with established epidemiological evidence linking typhoid transmission to unsafe water and poor hygiene (Akinyemi et al., 2018; Ilouno, 2020). However, the coexistence of biomedical knowledge with persistent misconceptions such as witchcraft and mosquito transmission points to the continued influence of socio-cultural beliefs on disease interpretation, as previously reported in Nigerian and African contexts (Smith et al., 2010).

The widespread awareness of typhoid-related surgical complications indicates that severe disease outcomes, including intestinal perforation, are not uncommon in the study area. This observation aligns with reports that delayed diagnosis, inappropriate treatment, and antimicrobial resistance contribute to advanced typhoid presentations in Nigeria (Akinyemi et al., 2018; Seyi-Olajide et al., 2020). The perceived frequent occurrence of typhoid further suggests endemic transmission rather than sporadic outbreaks, consistent with studies linking persistent typhoid transmission to environmental exposure and seasonal climatic factors such as rainfall and temperature (Ekpenyong & Akpan, 2023; Okeke & Eze, 2021; Nwidu et al., 2020).

Although hospital-based care was the most commonly reported treatment option and the primary first point of care for most respondents, the substantial reliance on herbal medicine and chemist shops highlights a critical gap between awareness and effective clinical management. Similar patterns have been documented in Nigeria, where cost, convenience, and cultural practices shape treatment choices and often lead to incomplete or inappropriate therapy (Smith et al., 2010; Akinyemi et al., 2018). The dominance of cost as the main reason for avoiding hospital care reinforces earlier findings that financial barriers remain a major determinant of health-seeking behaviour in low-income communities (Mogasale et al., 2014).

The high proportion of respondents who believe typhoid can be fatal is encouraging and suggests that risk perception is relatively strong. However, the persistence of uncertainty among a minority of respondents may still contribute to delayed care-seeking and reliance on informal treatment pathways. Beliefs surrounding recurrent typhoid infections further reveal that while most respondents understand the role of poor water and sanitation, some shift toward supernatural explanations when infections recur, a phenomenon previously described in settings where treatment failure and reinfection are common (Antillón et al., 2017).

Confidence in local health centres was generally high, which likely explains the preference for hospitals as the first point of care. Nevertheless, the continued occurrence of severe complications suggests that trust alone is insufficient when structural barriers—particularly cost, distance, and limited diagnostic capacity—remain unaddressed (Akinyemi et al., 2018; Seyi-Olajide et al., 2020). Attitudes toward integrating traditional and orthodox medicine reveal a divided community, reflecting ongoing debates around medical pluralism in African health systems, where traditional practices coexist with biomedical care but are not always harmonized (Smith et al., 2010).

The challenges driving alternative medicine use emphasize that typhoid persistence in Pankshin LGA is less a problem of complete ignorance and more a reflection of environmental exposure, economic hardship, and systemic health-system limitations. These findings mirror national and regional evidence that improving water and sanitation infrastructure, strengthening primary healthcare, and reducing financial barriers are critical to reducing typhoid burden in Nigeria and West Africa (Akinyemi et al., 2018; Ilouno, 2020; Ekpenyong & Akpan, 2023).

Implications for Public Health

The persistence of typhoid fever in rural communities of Pankshin LGA has significant implications for public health planning, policy, and practice. The strong link between typhoid occurrence and environmental factors such as unsafe water sources, poor sanitation, and inadequate waste disposal highlights the urgent need for strengthened water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) interventions. Without sustained improvements in environmental health infrastructure, typhoid transmission will continue despite clinical treatment efforts.

The study also reveals that misconceptions about the causes and transmission of typhoid fever remain prevalent, including beliefs in non-biomedical causes. This shows the importance of targeted health education and risk communication, particularly through community health nurses and primary healthcare workers, to correct misinformation and promote preventive practices such as safe food handling, water treatment, and personal hygiene.

Barriers to timely and appropriate treatment-seeking—especially cost of care, distance to health facilities, and reliance on herbal remedies or chemist shops—have serious public health consequences. Delayed care increases the risk of complications, prolonged transmission within households and communities, and preventable morbidity and mortality. These findings point to the need for strengthening primary

healthcare services, improving geographic and financial access to care, and ensuring the availability of affordable diagnostics and effective treatment at the community level.

The frequent reporting of severe complications requiring surgical intervention suggests gaps in early detection and case management. This has implications for health system preparedness, as preventable complications place additional strain on already limited surgical and referral services. Enhancing diagnostic capacity at lower levels of care and promoting early presentation can significantly reduce disease severity and healthcare costs.

Furthermore, the environmental and socio-cultural drivers identified in the study support the adoption of an eco-health or One Health approach to typhoid control. Integrating environmental management, community engagement, public health surveillance, and clinical care is essential for sustainable disease reduction. GIS-based mapping used in the study also demonstrates the value of spatial data for identifying high-risk areas, guiding targeted interventions, and improving outbreak preparedness and response.

Overall, the study implies that typhoid fever control in rural Nigerian settings cannot rely solely on medical treatment. Effective public health action must combine environmental improvements, community-centered health education, accessible and affordable healthcare services, and evidence-based surveillance to break the cycle of transmission and reduce the long-term burden of the disease.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that typhoid fever remains a persistent and serious public health problem in rural communities of Pankshin Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria. Although a substantial proportion of respondents possess basic knowledge of typhoid transmission particularly the role of contaminated water and food this knowledge coexists with persistent socio-cultural misconceptions, including beliefs in witchcraft and other non-biomedical causes. The frequent occurrence of typhoid reported by respondents, alongside widespread awareness of severe complications such as intestinal perforation requiring surgery, indicates ongoing endemic transmission and delayed or inadequate disease management within the communities. The findings further reveal a complex pattern of health-seeking behaviour. While hospitals are generally the preferred first point of care and confidence in local health centres is relatively high, a significant proportion of the population still relies on informal treatment pathways, including herbal medicine, prayers/spiritism and chemist shops. Financial constraints, distance to health facilities, and perceived effectiveness of alternative treatments emerged as major barriers to timely and appropriate clinical care. These barriers contribute to delayed presentation, incomplete treatment, and increased risk of severe complications. Overall, the study highlights that typhoid persistence in Pankshin LGA is driven not only by gaps in knowledge but more critically by structural, economic, and environmental constraints that limit the translation of awareness into effective prevention and treatment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend that typhoid control efforts in Pankshin LGA and similar rural settings adopt an integrated and context-specific approach. Priority should be given to improving access to safe drinking water and sanitation infrastructure to address the environmental conditions sustaining repeated transmission. Strengthening primary healthcare services through the provision of affordable diagnostic testing, essential medicines, and trained personnel is crucial to promote early detection and effective treatment.

In addition, community-based health education programs should be intensified, with a focus on correcting persistent misconceptions about typhoid causation, emphasizing the dangers of delayed treatment, and discouraging inappropriate self-medication. Given the strong influence of cost on health-seeking behaviour, policies that subsidize typhoid diagnosis and treatment, particularly for low-income households, are strongly recommended. Engagement with traditional and informal healthcare providers as referral partners may also help reduce delays by encouraging prompt hospital presentation. Collectively, these measures are essential to reducing the burden of typhoid fever, preventing severe complications, and improving overall health outcomes in rural Nigerian communities.

References

- Adeleye, I. A., & Adetosoye, A. I. (1993). Antimicrobial resistance patterns and plasmid survey of Salmonella and Shigella isolated in Ibadan, Nigeria. *East African medical journal*, 70(5), 259-262.
- Akinyemi, K. O., Oyefolu, A. O. B., Mutiu, W. B., Iwalokun, B. A., Ayeni, E. S., Ajose, S. O., & Obaro, S. K. (2018). Typhoid fever: tracking the trend in Nigeria. *The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene*, 99(3 Suppl), 41.
- Akinyemi, K. O., Smith, S. I., Oyefolu, A. B., & Coker, A. O. (2005). Multidrug resistance in Salmonella enterica serovar typhi isolated from patients with typhoid fever complications in Lagos, Nigeria. *Public health*, 119(4), 321-327.
- Akpenpuun, J. R., & Mpem, T. (2015). Note: Cited in text as Akpenpuun & Mpem, 2015, but full bibliographic details were partially missing from your list. It usually refers to: Perception of malaria and treatment seeking behaviour among rural dwellers in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 4, 1–6.
- Ameh, I. G., & Opara, W. E. K. (2004). Typhoid: a record of cases in Sokoto, Nigeria.
- Antillón, M., Warren, J. L., Crawford, F. W., Weinberger, D. M., Kürüm, E., Pak, G. D., ... & Pitzer, V. E. (2017). The burden of typhoid fever in low-and middle-income countries: a meta-regression approach. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 11(2), e0005376.
- Asenowo, A. O., & Adeoye, B. (2025). Factors Influencing Malaria and Typhoid Treatment And Health Seeking Behavior Among Rural Dwellers In Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Social Health*, 2(2).
- Breiman, R. F., Cosmas, L., Njuguna, H., Audi, A., Olack, B., Ochieng, J. B., ... & Feikin, D. R. (2012). Population-based incidence of typhoid fever in an urban informal settlement and a rural area in Kenya: implications for typhoid vaccine use in Africa. *PloS one*, 7(1), e29119.
- Buckle, G. C., Walker, C. L. F., & Black, R. E. (2012). Typhoid fever and paratyphoid fever: Systematic review to estimate global morbidity and mortality for 2010. *Journal of global health*, 2(1), 010401.
- Buzilă, E. R., Dorneanu, O. S., Trofin, F., Sima, C. M., & Iancu, L. S. (2025). Assessing Salmonella Typhi pathogenicity and Prevention: The crucial role of vaccination in combating Typhoid fever. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 26(9), 3981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26093981>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (2020). Note: Cited in text as CDC, 2020, regarding global typhoid cases.
- Ekpenyong, N; Akpan, M (2023). Climate Change Adaptation and Public Health Interventions in Nigeria: A Review. *Afr. J. Environ. Health*, 12(1), 45-58.

- Feasey, N. A., Dougan, G., Kingsley, R. A., Heyderman, R. S., & Gordon, M. A. (2012). Invasive nontyphoidal salmonella disease: an emerging and neglected tropical disease in Africa. *The Lancet*, 379(9835), 2489-2499.
- Hall, R. P., Van Koppen, B., & Van Houweling, E. (2014). The human right to water: the importance of domestic and productive water rights. *Science and engineering ethics*, 20(4), 849-868.
- Ia, S., & Mo, A. (2020b). Prevalence of malaria and typhoid coinfection in relation to haematological profile of university students in Akure, Nigeria. *Journal of Infectious Diseases and Epidemiology*, 6(5). <https://doi.org/10.23937/2474-3658/1510166>
- Ilouno, G. (2020). *Perceptions, Practices, and Risk Factors Associated With Typhoid Fever in Nimo Village, Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Kabir'O, A., Cokerb, A. O., Amorighoye, P., & Omonigbehinc, E. O. (2000). Prevalence of multi-drug resistant Salmonella typhi among clinically diagnosed typhoid fever patients in Lagos, Nigeria. *Z. Naturforsch*, 55, 489-493.
- Kingsley, O. C., Ifeanyi, A. O., Edet, A. E., & Smart, O. C. (2013). Bacteriologic profile and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of suspected septicaemic patients in Uyo, Nigeria. *Res J Med Sci*, 7(2), 35-39.
- Marks, F., von Kalckreuth, V., Aaby, P., Adu-Sarkodie, Y., El Tayeb, M. A., Ali, M., ... & Wierzba, T. F. (2017). Incidence of invasive salmonella disease in sub-Saharan Africa: a multicentre population-based surveillance study. *The Lancet Global Health*, 5(3), e310-e323
- Mogasale, V., Maskery, B., Ochiai, R. L., Lee, J. S., Mogasale, V. V., Ramani, E., ... & Wierzba, T. F. (2014). Burden of typhoid fever in low-income and middle-income countries: a systematic, literature-based update with risk-factor adjustment. *The Lancet Global Health*, 2(10), e570-e580.
- Mogasale, V., Mogasale, V. V., Ramani, E., Lee, J. S., Park, J. Y., Lee, K. S., & Wierzba, T. F. (2015). Revisiting typhoid fever surveillance in low and middle income countries: lessons from systematic literature review of population-based longitudinal studies. *BMC infectious diseases*, 16(1), 35.
- Nas, F. S., Ali, M., & Yahaya, A. (2017). Malaria and typhoid fever co-infection among febrile patients in Kumbotso Local Government Area Kano, Nigeria. *Bayero Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 10(2), 122-125.
- National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] & ICF. (2019). Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018. NPC and ICF. (Cited in text as Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey, 2018).
- Nwankwo, B. J., Joseph, J., & Aronu, E. U. (2024). Investigation Into The Lipid Profile Of Goat Serum In Pankshin Town. *Anspoly Journal of Advanced Research in Science & Technology (AJARST)*, 1(2), 69-82.
- Nwidu, LL; Ekeke, C; Ogu, CN; (2020). Climate variability and waterborne diseases in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *J. Environ. Health. Res.* 15(3), 142-155.
- Obaro, S. K., Hassan-Hanga, F., Olateju, E. K., Umoru, D., Lawson, L., Olanipekun, G., ... & Fey, P. D. (2015). Salmonella bacteremia among children in central and northwest Nigeria, 2008-2015. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 61(suppl_4), S325-S331.
- Oboegbulam, S. I., Oguike, J. U., & Gugnani, H. C. (1995). Microbiological studies on cases diagnosed as typhoid/enteric fever in south-east Nigeria. *The Journal of Communicable Diseases*, 27(2), 97-100.
- Ogbonna, AC; Chukwu, KE; Obinna, FN (2023). Rainfall, sanitation, and typhoid fever outbreaks in Enugu, Nigeria. *Environ.l Health. Perspect.* 31(2), 85-97.

- Okeke, OC; Eze, EO (2021). Water contamination and public health risk during the rainy season in Umuahia, Nigeria. *J. Wat. Health.* 19(2), 203–215.
- Oladimeji, K. E., Tsoka-Gwegweni, J. M., Gengiah, S., Daftery, A., & Naidoo, K. (2018). Barriers to effective uptake of malaria prevention interventions in Ibadan, South West Nigeria: A qualitative study. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 5(4), 1304–1310.
- Omoregie, A. E., & Okoro, E. O. (2024). Local Climate Conditions and Prevalence of Typhoid Fever Disease Patterns in a Vulnerable Community of Ikpoba Okha LGA of Edo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 28(11), 3731-3736.
- Seyi-Olajide, J. O., Anderson, J., Enivwaene, A. O., Ibrahim, S. H., Farmer, D., & Ameh, E. A. (2020). Catastrophic healthcare expenditure from typhoid perforation in children in Nigeria. *Surgical Infections*, 21(7), 586-591.
- Simon-Oke, I. A., & Akinbote, M. O. (2020). Prevalence of malaria and typhoid co-infection in relation to haematological profile of university students in Akure Nigeria. *Journal of Infectious Diseases and Epidemiology*, 6, 166.
- Smith, S. I., Agomo, C. O., Bamidele, M., Opere, B. O., & Aboaba, O. O. (2010). Survey of food handlers in bukas (a type of local restaurant) in Lagos, Nigeria about typhoid fever.
- Steele, A. D., Hay Burgess, D. C., Diaz, Z., Carey, M. E., & Zaidi, A. K. (2016). Challenges and opportunities for typhoid fever control: a call for coordinated action. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 62(suppl_1), S4-S8.
- Talabi, H. A. (1994). Medical aspects of typhoid. *Niger Postgrad Med J*, 1, 51-56.
- Ubengama, N. E., Useh, M. F., & Ben, S. A. (2019). High occurrence of typhoid fever and malaria co-infection among patients clinically diagnosed of malaria and or typhoid infection in Calabar, Nigeria. *Journal of Medical Laboratory Science*, 29(2), 1-9.
- United Nations. (2022). Worldometer report of the United Nations data on the latest population of Nigeria.
- Wafula, J. P. (2022). Perceived environmental risks and hazards in urban poor communities and associated health outcomes: An Ecohealth study of the Odawna community in Accra, Ghana. *ScienceOpen Preprints*.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2015). Global technical strategy for malaria 2016-2030. World Health Organization.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2017). Malaria prevention works, let's close the gap. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- World Health Organization (WHO). (2020). World Malaria Report 2020: 20 years of progress and challenges. World Health Organization.
- World Health Organization, (2014). World Malaria Report 2014. Geneva, World Heal. The Organ
- World Health Organization. (2008). Typhoid vaccines: WHO position paper= Vaccins antityphoïdiques: note d'information de l'OMS. *Weekly Epidemiological Record= Relevé épidémiologique hebdomadaire*, 83(06), 49-59.

